

Kinetic Studies on Metalloporphyrin Formation in Aqueous Solutions of *meso*-Tetra(*p*-sulphonatophenyl)-porphyrin and some Metal(II) Ions

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Studies on kinetics of metalloporphyrin formation in weakly acidic aqueous solution (pH 3.8–4.7) in perchlorate medium have been carried out spectrophotometrically at 435 nm for the reactions of $M(H_2O)_6^{2+}$ ($M = Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu$) with *meso*-tetra(*p*-sulphonatophenyl)prophyrin, $TPPS^{4-}$. The results have been compared with the corresponding reactions of *meso*-tetra(4-*N*-methylpyridyl)porphyrin and the water exchange rates of the aqua-metal(II) ions. Compared to water exchange rates, reduction in the rate of formation of metalloporphyrin with $TPPS^{4-}$ is by a factor of 10^7 to 10^{10} , the minimum and maximum values being observed with Ni^{II} and Mn^{II} respectively. The results have been interpreted on the basis of the general mechanism for metalloporphyrin formation.

Metal-porphyrins mimic the metal bonded moiety of several naturally occurring complexes of biological significance. The chemistry of such compounds provide a fertile ground for kinetic investigations and some such work have been reported¹⁻⁵. The present work reports the results of investigations on the kinetics of formation of water soluble complexes of some metal(II) ions of the first transition series with *meso*-tetra(*p*-sulphonatophenyl)prophyrin ($TPPS^{4-} = LH_2^{4-}$) in weakly acidic aqueous solution in perchlorate medium where all the free metal(II) ions exist as $M(H_2O)_6^{2+}$. Use of a perchlorate medium was particularly necessary since ligands like OH^- , NO_3^- , CH_3COO^- , etc. bound to the metal ion are known to have profound catalytic effect on metal ion incorporation in porphyrins^{2,5}. Since for Fe^{2+} a solution of Mohr's salt was used there was a low concentration of SO_4^{2-} in the medium which, however, had no effect.

Results and Discussion

The observed dependence of k_{obs} on $[H^+]$ and total metal concentration $[M^{2+}]_T$ ($[M^{2+}]_T \gg [TPPS^{4-}]_T$) is in agreement with the following reaction scheme

LH_3^{3-} is the porphyrin species in which a H^+ is bound to one of the basic tertiary N of the porphyrin ring. From equations (1) and (2) it can be easily shown that

$$k_{obs} = k_f K_3 [M^{2+}]_T / (K_3 + [H^+]) \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) on rearrangement leads to

$$[M^{2+}]_T / k_{obs} = 1/k_f + [H^+] / (k_f K_3) \quad (4)$$

In accordance with equation (3) at any fixed pH, the plot of k_{obs} vs $[M^{2+}]_T$ has been found to be linear for each of the metal ions at different temperatures. From the linear plot of $[M^{2+}]_T / k_{obs}$ vs $[H^+]$ the values of k_f and K_3 could be evaluated and all such values are given in Table 1, with the corresponding ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger values evaluated from the k_f values at different temperatures using Eyring equation⁶ as usual. For clarity only a few of the

TABLE 1—VALUES OF k_f AND K_3 AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES FOR METALLOPORPHYRIN FORMATION BY $M(H_2O)_6^{2+}$ WITH $TPPS^{4-}$ IN WEAKLY ACIDIC AQUEOUS SOLUTION (pH 3.8–4.7) AT $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ ($NaClO_4$)

M^{2+}	Temp. °C	$k_f, \text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$	$10^5 K_3, \text{mol dm}^{-3}$		
Mn^{2+}	50	0.20 ± 0.01	7.08 ± 0.02		
	55	0.30 ± 0.01	9.56 ± 0.03		
	60	0.48 ± 0.01	13.60 ± 0.04		
	65	0.71 ± 0.02	16.80 ± 0.05		
Fe^{2+}	50	0.53 ± 0.01	7.12 ± 0.04		
	55	0.67 ± 0.02	9.60 ± 0.05		
	60	0.83 ± 0.02	13.30 ± 0.06		
	65	1.00 ± 0.02	16.70 ± 0.06		
Co^{2+}	50	0.48 ± 0.01	7.08 ± 0.02		
	55	0.62 ± 0.01	9.88 ± 0.03		
	60	0.76 ± 0.02	13.20 ± 0.05		
	65	0.93 ± 0.02	16.50 ± 0.04		
Ni^{2+}	50	0.026 ± 0.001	7.08 ± 0.03		
	60	0.036 ± 0.002	13.30 ± 0.05		
	65	0.042 ± 0.002	16.70 ± 0.04		
	70	0.048 ± 0.003	22.00 ± 0.06		
Cu^{2+}	35	10.00 ± 0.31	2.82 ± 0.01		
	40	11.76 ± 0.29	3.62 ± 0.01		
	45	13.36 ± 0.33	4.55 ± 0.02		
	50	15.40 ± 0.35	7.10 ± 0.02		
	Mn^{2+}	Fe^{2+}	Co^{2+}	Ni^{2+}	Cu^{2+}
$\Delta H^{\ddagger b}, \text{kJ mol}^{-1}$	77.0 ± 1.6	35.4 ± 0.7	34.2 ± 0.7	26.7 ± 0.5	20.9 ± 0.4
$\Delta S^{\ddagger b}, \text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$	-22.4 ± 0.4	-142.5 ± 3.5	-146.6 ± 3.5	-194.8 ± 4.9	-159.3 ± 4.1

^aThese K_3 values lead to $\Delta H = 52.0 \pm 0.6 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $\Delta S = 81.0 \pm 1.4 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$.

^bCorresponds to the k_f in each case.

$[M^{2+}]_T/k_{obs}$ vs $[H^+]$ plots, at two different temperatures for each of the metal ions, are shown in Fig. 1.

For the purpose of comparison, the k_f values were calculated for 25° using the evaluated ΔH^{\ddagger} and ΔS^{\ddagger} values. These k_f (25°) values are given in Table 2 together with the corresponding values (at 22°) reported in literature^{3,5} for the reactions of *meso*-tetra(4-*N*-methylpyridyl)porphyrin ($TMPyP^{4+}$) and the rate constants for the water exchange reactions of the aqua-metal ions at 25° ⁷. From the data (Table 2) the following relative values of the rates are obtained :

$$(k_{ex}^{M^{2+}}/k_{ex}^{Ni^{2+}})_{25^\circ} : 1.0 \times 10^3 \text{ (Mn)}; 1.0 \times 10^2 \text{ (Fe)}; 56.3 \text{ (Co)}; 6.3 \times 10^4 \text{ (Cu)}$$

$$(k_f^{M(II)-TPPS}/k_f^{Ni(II)-TPPS})_{25^\circ} : 1.6 \text{ (Mn)}; 17 \text{ (Fe)}; 16 \text{ (Co)}; 745 \text{ (Cu)}$$

$$(k_f^{M(II)-TMPyP}/k_f^{Ni(II)-TMPyP})_{22^\circ} :$$

$$50 \text{ (Mn)}; 44 \text{ (Co)}; 4.6 \times 10^4 \text{ (Cu)}$$

$$(k_f^{M(II)-TPPS}/k_{ex}^{M(II)})_{25^\circ} : 5.0 \times 10^{-10} \text{ (Mn)};$$

$$5.3 \times 10^{-8} \text{ (Fe)}; 8.9 \times 10^{-8} \text{ (Co)}; 3.1 \times 10^{-7} \text{ (Ni)}; 3.7 \times 10^{-9} \text{ (Cu)}$$

$$k_f^{M(II)-TMPyP} (22^\circ) / k_{ex}^{M(II)} (25^\circ) : 0.8 \times 10^{-10} \text{ (Mn)};$$

$$1.2 \times 10^{-9} \text{ (Co)}; 1.6 \times 10^{-9} \text{ (Ni)}; 1.2 \times 10^{-9} \text{ (Cu)}$$

$$k_f^{M(II)-TPPS} (25^\circ) / k_f^{M(II)-TMPyP} (22^\circ) : 6.4 \text{ (Mn)};$$

$$72.7 \text{ (Co)}; 200 \text{ (Ni)}; 3.2 \text{ (Cu)}$$

Thus, while the reaction of Cu^{2+} is the fastest and that of Ni^{2+} is the slowest in all the cases, the ratio of k_f for formation of the Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes of $TPPS^{4-}$ is only 745 at 25° as against

which is one of the factors responsible for slowing down the reaction; it is known that complex formation by a protonated ligand is much slower than complex formation with the corresponding free ligand by a factor of between 10^2 to 10^6 in many cases⁹. Apart from this, the following are also contributing factors. In the formation of species I, the K_{os} may not be as large as is expected theoretically for interaction between a cationic species of charge $2+$ and an anionic species of charge $4-$, since in case of the bulky TPPS⁴⁻ the negative charge resides in the peripheral SO_3^- groups in the phenyl substituents, while for effective reaction the outersphere association may be essentially due to the interaction between the $M(H_2O)_6^{2+}$ ion and the four uncharged N sites in the porphyrin ring. The equilibrium constant K_D for the deformation process is also likely to have a low value, as also the equilibrium constant K_1 leading to formation of the species III which is most likely to be a 'sitting atop' type of complex with loss of two aqua-ligands from the inner coordination sphere of the metal ion. The cumulative effect of all these is the very low value for k_f .

Experimental

The ligand *meso*-tetra(*p*-sulphonatophenyl)porphyrin was prepared as its ammonium salt, $C_{44}H_{20}N_4(SO_3)_4(NH_4)_4 \cdot 9H_2O$, in pure form by known method¹⁰ from *meso*-tetraphenylporphyrin¹¹ and its purity was checked by chemical analysis of the constituent elements C, H, N and S by standard methods. All the solutions of metal ions, except Fe^{2+} , were prepared using perchlorate salts, while for Fe^{2+} Mohr's salt (AnalaR) was used. The solutions were prepared in double-distilled water, second distillation being carried out from alkaline permanganate in all-glass still, and were standardised by known methods¹². For ionic strength adjustment, $NaClO_4$ twice recrystallised from water and dried at 130° was used. For pH adjustment, $HClO_4$ (G.R., E. Merck) or $NaOH$ (G.R., E. Merck) were used as needed.

pH measurements were made using Systronics 335 (India) pH meter with glass-calomel combination electrode assembly set with standard solutions of known pH values and the system was calibrated

with solutions of known $[H^+]$ at different temperatures so that from the measured pH values of the experimental solutions the corresponding $[H^+]$ could be ascertained.

Spectra of the ligand and the metal complexes at different pH were recorded using a Carl-Zeiss spectrophotometer (VSU-2P, Jena, Germany). In slow reacting systems the kinetics of complexation of metal ion with the ligand (TPPS⁴⁻) were followed by conventional spectrophotometry at 435 nm (absorbance maximum for the ligand) where the metal complexes formed are far less absorbing. For the reaction of Cu^{2+} (which occurs very much more rapidly), lower experimental temperatures were used and the kinetics followed by stopped-flow spectrophotometry using a commercial instrument (SF-3A, Hi-Tech, England) coupled with a transient recorder (DL-905, Data Lab, England) and a chart recorder (PL-3, J. J. Lloyds, England). The instrument had facility for thermostating the experimental solutions, mixing chamber and observation cell for constant temperature ($\pm 0.05^\circ$) work.

In case of reactions of Mn^{2+} , Fe^{2+} and Co^{2+} , the kinetic studies were carried out in presence of moderate excess of $NH_2OH \cdot HCl$ (0.05 mol dm^{-3}) in the experimental solutions to exclude the possibility of oxidation of these metals to higher valence states. The experiments were all performed under pseudo-first order conditions keeping the concentration of M^{2+} much in excess of the ligand, TPPS⁴⁻ ($5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$). The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) for formation of the metalloporphyrins were evaluated by the method of least-squares using absorbance vs time data for the reactions. For k_{obs} average of three independent determinations was used in each case. Experiments were performed at different pH (in the range 3.8–4.7) as well as different concentrations of M^{2+} (5×10^{-4} to $4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$).

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